

As panicles with more primary branches accommodate more HD grains, substantial heterosis for that

character may lead to higher yield. The three crosses with IR30 (P2) as a common parent in either direction

(P5/ P2, P1 / P2, and P2/ P9) had positive heterosis for panicles with more primary branches. □

Table 2. Heterosis percentage of 9 quantitative yield characters. IRRI, 1988.

Character	Heterosis (%) in given cross ^a							LSD (0.05)
	P1/P2 (HD/HD)	P3/P4 (HD/HD)	P5/P2 (HD/HD)	P2/P6 (HD/HD)	P4/P7 (HD/HD)	P3/P8 (HD/LD)	P2/P9 (HD/LD)	
Primary branches	5.21	1.69	9.42	-1.38	-7.23	-9.31	3.35	1.82
Secondary branches	0	9.77	4.75	6.00	23.63	-5.93	35.34	6.75
Tertiary branches	-39.39	-80.95	-100.00	11.11	80.00	12.00	150.00	27.00
Spikelets on primary branches	13.64	1.31	15.36	-7.49	-18.48	-2.38	4.25	3.66
Spikelets on secondary branches	0.67	11.78	4.89	15.63	32.85	-2.33	28.69	6.83
Spikelets on tertiary branches	-56.96	-88.73	-100.00	33.33	62.50	-18.99	122.00	19.70
Total spikelets	3.50	5.90	7.92	6.09	11.82	-2.67	19.51	3.12
Inner vascular bundles	4.86	2.15	1.07	1.73	-1.39	-0.44	9.33	1.68
Outer vascular bundles	1.79	-4.81	-11.34	-1.37	-11.24	-1.38	3.27	2.38

^aP1 = IR32307-75-1-3-1, P2 = IR30, P3 = IR34615-75-1-1, P4 = IR29725-135-2-2-3, P5 = IR29692-117-1-2-2, P6 = IR35337-61-2-2-2, P7 = IR28211-43-1-1-1-2, P8 = IR32419-102-3-2-3, P9 = IR32385-37-3-3-3.

Influence of silicon and its antagonists on rice mitochondria

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Silicon is beneficial to rice plant growth and development, but the mechanisms of its biological activity are obscure.

Si physiological antagonists As and Ge suppress rice plant growth and dry matter accumulation and induce necrosis. We studied rice mitochondria morphology to test the assumption that Si can stabilize and As and Ge can damage the energy-producing systems of the rice cells.

Rice variety Krasnodarsky 424 seedlings were grown to the 2-leaf stage in water culture, with 60 μmol Si in treatment 1, 60 μmol Ge in treatment 2, and 60 μmol As in treatment 3. Mitochondria were isolated with the sediments in 0.05 M tris-HCl; 0.01 M EDTA; 0.05% cystein (pH 7.4) buffer. The isolated mitochondria were fixed with gluteraldehyde and osmiate, contrasted with uranylacetate, stained

Mitochondrion in treatment with 60 μmol Si (a) and 60 μmol Ge (b), and destruction of spherical mitochondrion (c).

with Pb-citrate, and studied under an electron microscope.

Mitochondria in the Si treatment were almost uniform, spherical particles 0.2-0.5 μm in diameter (see figure). Mitochondria in the Ge suspension were about 50% smaller and elongated. Material of different electron densities distributed sporadically on the surface can be explained as either injury of

the surface membrane or as Ge accumulation in the surface membrane.

The As suspension showed about 40% destruction of the spherical mitochondrion. That can be explained by the As mechanism of arsenolysis of macroergical compounds, leading to mitochondria membrane degradation. □

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Grain quality and nutritional value

Grain quality of new Pakistani rice lines

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Four promising lines—AS688, IR25588-7-3-1, IR28128-45-2, and PND160-2-1—from the 1985 Irrigated Rice Yield Nursery-Very Early yielded higher than local varieties grown in Mansehra and Muzaffarabad. The lines were further tested 1986-87 in microplot trials.

On the basis of total milling recovery, physical dimensions, chemical properties, and cooking and eating quality, AS688 resembled JP5, IR28128-45-2 resembled DR83, and PND160-2-1 resembled KS282 (see table).

The new lines are likely to be acceptable to local millers and consumers. □

Grain characteristics of 4 early-maturing rice lines and 3 local commercial varieties.^a Pakistan, 1985-87.

Entry	Total recovery (%)	Head rice (%)	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	Length-to-breadth ratio	Size/shape ^b	Grain thickness (mm)	Quality index ($\frac{L}{B \times T}$)
<i>Lines</i>								
AS688	67.8	42.4	5.3	2.6	2.0	S/B	2.0	1.0
IR25588-7-3-1	69.0	63.8	6.3	2.1	3.0	M/M	1.8	1.7
IR28128-45-2	66.2	59.8	6.6	1.9	3.5	L/S	1.6	2.2
PND160-2-1	64.0	47.0	6.6	1.7	3.9	L/S	1.6	2.4
<i>Local varieties</i>								
DR83	66.8	54.4	6.8	2.0	3.4	L/S	1.9	1.8
JP5	72.8	55.2	4.9	2.8	1.8	S/B	2.3	0.8
KS282	69.6	58.3	7.0	2.0	3.5	L/S	1.8	2.0
	Chalky grain (%)	Elongation ratio	Cooked grain appearance ^c		Protein (N × 5.95) % (db)	Amylose (% basis)	Alkali spreading value	Gelatinization temperature ^d (alkali basis)
<i>Lines</i>								
AS688	10	1.8	S		8.3	19	6.4	L
IR25588-7-3-1	6	1.5	S/S		7.9	23	5.9	I
IR28128-45-2	4	1.4	SE		8.0	25	7.0	L
PND160-2-1	5	1.8	W/SE		8.3	27	7.0	L
<i>Local varieties</i>								
DR83	8	1.6	SE		8.5	22	5.2	I
JP5	4	1.7	S		8.6	18	6.3	L
KS282	Nil	2.0	SE		8.3	28	7.0	L

^aAv of 3 replications. ^bS/B = short/bold, M/M = medium/medium, L/S = long/slender. ^cS = sticky, S/S = slightly sticky, SE = separated, W/SE = well separated. ^dL = low, I = intermediate.

Disease resistance

Scoring systems for evaluating rice varietal resistance to bacterial blight (BB): lesion size by growth stage

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Host plant resistance to pathogens can be measured using different parameters—latent period, pathogen

sporulation and growth in host tissues. In most cases, disease symptoms (lesion area, length, etc.) are scored according to an indexing scale based on the assumption that the lesion reflects pathogen growth in the host quantitatively, as a response of the host to infection.

We measured lesion development at different growth stages on 22 rice cultivars grown in pots in the greenhouse and infected with BB isolate PXO61 of race 1.

Planting was staggered to synchronize inoculation at different growth stages.

Total leaf area was measured using a leaf area meter at 11, 14, and 17 d after inoculation. Lesions were cut from individual leaves, the lesion area measured, and percentage infected leaf area calculated.

The cultivars were classified into three groups. Group 1 (including TN1) was highly susceptible at 20 d after sowing (DAS), but the lesion areas gradually decreased from 30 to 50 DAS and became constant from 50 to 80 DAS (see table). In group 2, lesion area decreased from 20 to 40 DAS but the plants remained susceptible. Lesions